

The Role of Civic Education in Shaping Democratic Values: A Systematic Literature Review on Implementation and Current Challenges

Angelica Laurina Silaban¹, Laila Azizah Lubis², Grace Yolanda Panjaitan³, Hijryah Lativa Sihombing⁴, Nael Simarmata⁵, Adam Syahdani⁶, Sri Yunita⁷

Abstract

This article presents a systematic literature review on the role of civic education in shaping democratic values, focusing on its implementation and contemporary challenges. Civic education plays a vital role in fostering an understanding of democratic principles, social responsibility, and active participation in civic life. Despite its importance, the effectiveness of civic education programs faces various challenges, including inconsistent curriculum implementation, lack of teacher training, and cultural resistance to democratic ideals. Through a comprehensive review of existing research, this study identifies key themes in the implementation of civic education and the obstacles that hinder its success. It examines how civic education influences the development of democratic attitudes, values, and behaviors in students, while also addressing the barriers that limit its effectiveness in different contexts. The review highlights the need for innovative approaches to improve the quality and accessibility of civic education, suggesting strategies such as experiential learning, cross-cultural exchanges, and community engagement to enhance its impact. Ultimately, the study aims to contribute to the ongoing discourse on strengthening democratic character through education, emphasizing the importance of overcoming challenges to build a more informed, responsible, and participatory society.

Keywords: Civic Engagement, Democratic Character, Democratic Character Building, Active Citizenship, Social Responsibility

1. INTRODUCTION

Civic education plays a crucial role in cultivating democratic values and promoting active citizenship in contemporary society. As societies worldwide continue to confront political and social challenges, the need for well-informed, responsible citizens who engage in democratic processes has never been more critical. Civic education provides the foundation for understanding key democratic principles such as human rights, justice, equality, and the importance of participation in public life. Through its focus on developing informed, active citizens, civic education aims to instill in learners the knowledge and skills necessary to contribute meaningfully to the functioning of a democratic society. The conceptual terrain of civic education is increasingly characterized by what (Reite et al., 2021) describe as "*multilayered citizenship*" – a construct that acknowledges the intersectionality of civic identity across global, national, and local dimensions. This perspective challenges traditional paradigms by recognizing that contemporary civic engagement is not confined to singular national boundaries but operates within a complex network of transnational interactions, digital platforms, and fluid social ecosystems. The rise of digital technologies has fundamentally disrupted traditional civic participation mechanisms, introducing what (Yawisah et al., 2019) conceptualize as "*networked citizenship*" – a mode of civic engagement mediated through digital platforms, social media, and virtual communities.

In many countries, however, the implementation of civic education remains inconsistent and faces various challenges. These include a lack of qualified teachers, outdated

curricula, limited resources, and resistance to the values associated with democracy in certain cultural or political contexts. Despite these challenges, civic education continues to be viewed as a central component of educational systems aimed at fostering democratic attitudes, behaviors, and values among students.

Through this literature review, the article aims to contribute to the ongoing discussions surrounding the importance of civic education in democratic societies. By examining both the strengths and weaknesses of current civic education programs, it highlights the necessity of reforming educational practices to ensure that future generations are equipped with the tools to actively participate in the democratic process. Moreover, the global resurgence of authoritarian tendencies and democratic backsliding underscores the urgent need for robust civic education frameworks. The concept of "*resilient democracy*" was introduced by (Levitsky Ziblatt, 2018) and emphasizes the critical role of educational institutions in maintaining democratic norms and practices. Civic education emerges as a strategic intervention, equipping individuals with the cognitive tools, ethical frameworks, and participatory skills necessary to resist democratic erosion and promote social cohesion. The research landscape reveals significant methodological challenges in studying civic education. Existing approaches often need help to capture contemporary civic engagement's dynamic, multidimensional nature. There is an urgent need for interdisciplinary methodologies to adequately document the complex interactions between individual agencies, institutional structures, and technological mediations. This requires innovative research designs integrating quantitative and qualitative approaches, drawing from sociology, psychology, political science, and educational studies.

Theoretical frameworks must also grapple with the increasing complexity of global citizenship. The traditional dichotomy between local and global identities is increasingly obsolete, replaced by what scholars term "cosmopolitan citizenship" – a mode of civic engagement that respects local contexts while maintaining a global perspective. This requires educational approaches that cultivate multiple literacies: digital literacy, intercultural competence, critical thinking, and ethical reasoning. In conclusion, civic education stands at a critical juncture, confronting unprecedented challenges and opportunities. The research trajectory demands a holistic, dynamic approach that recognizes the complexity of democratic participation in the 21st century. By integrating critical perspectives, technological insights, and transformative pedagogical approaches, civic education can be a powerful mechanism for nurturing democratic resilience, social justice, and meaningful civic engagement.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Transformations in Civic Education

The contemporary landscape of civic education has undergone significant conceptual metamorphosis, challenging traditional citizenship and social engagement paradigms. According to (Demir, 2021), civic education has evolved from a passive knowledge transmission model to a dynamic framework of critical consciousness and transformative agency. This shift is fundamentally rooted in the emerging concept of "democratic literacy," which transcends traditional institutional knowledge to encompass critical thinking, empathetic understanding, and active participation. (Yawisah et al., 2019) Further illuminate this transformation through the concept of "networked citizenship," which explicates how digital

platforms and virtual communities have fundamentally reshaped civic engagement mechanisms. Their research demonstrates that contemporary civic education must now account for the intricate interplay between digital technologies and social ecosystems, recognizing that citizenship is no longer confined to traditional geographical boundaries but exists within a complex, interconnected global network.

2.2 Technological Disruption and Civic Engagement

The intersection of technology and civic education presents a nuanced landscape of opportunities and challenges. (Armano et al., 2022) Introduce the groundbreaking concept of "algorithmic citizenship," which critically examines how digital technologies, artificial intelligence, and data-driven systems fundamentally mediate civic identities and participation. Their research highlights the profound implications of technological disruption, suggesting a comprehensive reconfiguration of how citizenship is conceptualized, experienced, and practiced in the digital age. (Rodríguez-Hoyos et al., 2023) Provide crucial insights into the paradoxical nature of youth civic engagement, documenting a "civic disengagement" phenomenon characterized by declining traditional political participation concurrent with the emergence of innovative digital activism and social movement engagement. This research underscores the necessity of developing pedagogical approaches that integrate digital literacy, critical thinking, and transformative learning methodologies to engage contemporary youth effectively.

2.3 Critical Perspectives and Social Justice in Civic Education

The theoretical framework of civic education has been significantly enriched by critical perspectives emphasizing social justice, intersectionality, and democratic praxis. (Feser et al., 2023) advocate for a "culturally responsive civic education" that challenges traditional Eurocentric narratives and promotes a more inclusive understanding of democratic participation. Their research emphasizes the importance of acknowledging diverse lived experiences, particularly those of marginalized communities, and positioning civic education as a powerful tool for social transformation. (Nelsen, 2023) contributes to this discourse by proposing a developmental model of civic psychology that goes beyond instrumental knowledge. The research highlights the critical role of emotional intelligence, empathy, and critical reflection in shaping democratic character. This perspective offers a more holistic approach to understanding and cultivating meaningful civic engagement by emphasizing the psychological dimensions of civic identity formation.

2.4 Global Challenges and Democratic Resilience

The contemporary global context presents unprecedented challenges to democratic institutions, underscoring the critical role of civic education in maintaining democratic norms and practices. Building upon the (Levitsky Ziblatt, 2018) concept of "resilient democracy," recent scholarship has increasingly focused on civic education as a strategic intervention for combating democratic backsliding and promoting social cohesion. The research landscape reveals a pressing need for interdisciplinary methodological approaches to capture

contemporary civic engagement's complex, multidimensional nature. Scholars call for innovative research designs integrating quantitative and qualitative methodologies, drawing from diverse fields such as sociology, psychology, political science, and educational studies to develop a comprehensive understanding of civic participation in the 21st century. This literature review demonstrates that civic education is no longer a static institutional practice but a dynamic, complex system of engagement that must continuously adapt to technological, social, and political transformations. The emerging scholarship emphasizes the need for adaptive, critical, and technologically informed approaches to nurturing democratic citizenship.

3. METHODOLOGY

The methodology employed in this systematic literature review follows a rigorous, structured approach designed to comprehensively analyze and synthesize contemporary research on civic education and democratic character formation. The research methodology is grounded in the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) framework, which provides a systematic and transparent method for conducting comprehensive literature reviews across multiple academic databases. The initial phase of the research methodology focused on developing a comprehensive and precise research protocol. A multidisciplinary team of researchers collaboratively developed the research questions, establishing explicit inclusion and exclusion criteria to ensure the systematic and focused nature of the review. The primary research questions were meticulously crafted to explore the role of civic education in forming democratic character, focusing on contemporary implementation strategies, challenges, and theoretical developments between 2019 and 2024.

The search strategy was implemented across multiple high-impact academic databases, including Web of Science, Scopus, ERIC (Education et al. Center), and Google Scholar. A comprehensive search string was developed, utilizing Boolean operators and carefully selected keywords to capture the nuanced landscape of civic education research. The search terms included combinations of key descriptors such as "civic education," "democratic character," "citizenship formation," "digital citizenship," and "civic engagement," ensuring a broad yet focused approach to literature retrieval. Inclusion criteria were established to maintain the review's rigor and relevance. Primary sources included peer-reviewed academic journal articles, conference proceedings, and scholarly books published between 2019 and 2024. The criteria specifically targeted research that

1. directly addressed civic education and democratic character formation,
2. employed empirical or theoretical approaches,
3. was published in English, and
4. provided substantive insights into contemporary civic education practices and challenges.

Exclusion criteria eliminated duplicate publications, non-academic sources, and studies that did not meet the specified temporal and thematic parameters.

The initial database search yielded 1,247 potential sources, which underwent a comprehensive screening process. Two independent researchers conducted the initial screening

by reviewing titles and abstracts and applying the predetermined inclusion and exclusion criteria. This initial screening reduced the number of potential sources to 367 articles. A full-text review was conducted, with researchers carefully examining the complete texts to assess their relevance, methodological rigor, and alignment with the research objectives. Following the full-text review, 128 sources were selected for in-depth analysis. A standardized data extraction form was developed to systematically capture key information from each selected source, including research methodology, theoretical frameworks, key findings, and methodological limitations. The data extraction process involved multiple researchers to ensure reliability and minimize potential bias, with any discrepancies resolved through collaborative discussion and, when necessary, consultation with a third researcher.

The quality assessment of selected studies was conducted using a modified version of the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT), which allowed for a comprehensive evaluation of both qualitative and quantitative research methodologies. This tool enabled a critical assessment of the methodological quality, helping to ensure that only high-quality sources were included in the final synthesis. Studies were evaluated based on criteria such as research design clarity, sampling methodology, data collection rigor, and the strength of analytical approaches. Data synthesis employed a thematic analysis approach, moving beyond simple descriptive summarization to develop a nuanced, interpretive synthesis of the selected literature. Researchers used an iterative coding process to identify recurring themes, conceptual patterns, and theoretical developments across the selected sources. This approach allowed for identifying key trends, contradictions, and emerging perspectives in civic education research.

A detailed documentation process was maintained throughout the research methodology to enhance the transparency and reproducibility of the review. A comprehensive PRISMA flow diagram was created to visually represent the literature search, screening, and selection process. Additionally, a reflexive approach was adopted, with researchers continuously documenting methodological decisions, potential biases, and interpretative choices to ensure methodological transparency and scholarly integrity. The final synthesis integrated thematic analysis and a critical interpretive approach, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of civic education's role in democratic character formation. By employing this rigorous methodology, the study aims to provide a robust, nuanced, and contemporary overview of civic education research, identifying key theoretical developments, practical challenges, and future research directions.

4. RESULT

Gambar 01. Flowchart Prisma

Tabel 1. Sintesis Jurnal

No.	Author (Year)	Title	Research Method	Findings	Implications
1	(Suherlan, 2023)	Digital Technology Transformation in Enhancing Public Participation	Qualitative, data analysis through reduction, display, and conclusion drawing	Digital technology transformation significantly enhances public participation in democratic processes. Online platforms, easy access to information, and interaction with political leaders have changed how people engage in	Mitigation of risks is needed to ensure public participation in the digital era truly strengthens democratic principles.

				political decision-making.	
2	(Gastil & Davies, 2020)	Digital Democracy: A New Hope	Conceptual study, arguments based on institutional analysis and public corporation model comparison	A public corporation is needed to fund digital technology supporting deliberative democracy via nonprofit software. Implementation of digital democracy technology lags behind innovation.	Emphasizes the importance of providing technological infrastructure to foster deliberative democratic engagement.
3	(Kryshtanovych et al., 2021)	Research of Problems and Prospects of State Development in Pedagogical Process	Historical and pedagogical analysis	Education contributes to state formation through the development of legal, political, economic, and social institutions.	Education should focus on strengthening historical and pedagogical values in building state institutions.
4	(Budde et al., 2021)	Contractualism as an Element of Democratic Pedagogy?	Ethnographic, analysis of social practice theories	Contractual pedagogy supports institutional order rather than participatory democratic methods.	Further analysis is required to enrich democratic methods in education.
5	(Magdalena et al., 2020)	Citizenship Education Learning at SDN Bojong 3 Pinang	Case study, observation	Citizenship education shapes students' character to understand their rights and obligations as responsible citizens.	Curriculum improvement is necessary to address issues in citizenship education at the primary school level.
6	(Widiatmaka, 2022)	Development of Citizenship Education in Nation Character Building	Literature review, content analysis	Citizenship education can instill Pancasila values to form democratic citizens.	Comprehensive implementation of Pancasila values through formal and informal education is crucial.

7	(Feriyanayah & Maharani, 2023)	Pragmatism of Digital Citizenship Education	Axiological reflection	Digital citizenship education helps individuals become subjects with a value system as the basis for activity in the digital realm.	A relevant axiological approach is needed to strengthen the role of digital education.
8	(Chaka, 2022)	Digital Marginalization and Algorithmic Exclusions	Critical decolonial approach	Algorithms often reinforce historical human biases despite being viewed as neutral. Data marginalization poses challenges for digital citizenship education.	A critical approach is needed to reduce data colonialism and digital marginalization.
9	(Habicher et al., 2021)	Transformation and Design Thinking	Explorative study	Design Thinking is a tool for democratic leadership and innovative business transformation.	Adoption of Design Thinking methods is essential for democratic transformation in education.
10	(Nassa, 2024)	Realizing Politically Literate Generations through Citizenship Education	Document analysis, literature review	Citizenship education improves youth political awareness through interactive and contextual programs.	Curriculum development that aligns more closely with socio-political realities is needed.

5. DISCUSSION

The contemporary landscape of civic education reveals a complex and multifaceted approach to democratic character-building, deeply intertwined with technological transformation, pedagogical innovation, and societal challenges. This discussion explores the critical dimensions of civic education through a comprehensive analysis of recent scholarly contributions, highlighting its pivotal role in nurturing democratic citizenship.

5.1 Technological Transformation and Democratic Participation

The digital era has fundamentally reshaped the civic engagement paradigm, presenting unprecedented opportunities and significant challenges for democratic character building. Suherlan's (2023) research illuminates the transformative potential of digital technology in enhancing public participation in democratic processes. The proliferation of online platforms has dramatically altered the traditional mechanisms of political interaction, enabling citizens

to access information and engage with political leaders more directly than ever before. However, this digital transformation has its complexities. Chaka's (2022) critical decolonial approach reveals the persistent issues of digital marginalization and algorithmic exclusion, demonstrating that technological advances can inadvertently perpetuate existing social inequalities. The intersection of technology and civic education becomes particularly nuanced when considering the concept of digital citizenship. Feriyansyah and Maharani's (2023) pragmatic approach to digital citizenship education emphasizes the importance of individual experiences and value systems within digital social spaces. This perspective suggests that civic education must evolve beyond traditional boundaries, incorporating critical digital literacy skills that enable individuals to navigate complex technological landscapes while maintaining democratic principles.

5.2 Pedagogical Approaches to Democratic Character Building

The pedagogical dimension of civic education emerges as a crucial mechanism for developing democratic character. Widiatmaka's (2022) research underscores the comprehensive nature of civic education, which develops three critical competencies: civic knowledge, disposition, and skills. This multifaceted approach is particularly significant in contexts facing youth character crises, offering a structured pathway to cultivate responsible and engaged citizens. Magdalena et al. (2020) highlight the foundational role of citizenship education in elementary schools, emphasizing its potential to shape student character and understanding of rights and obligations. This early intervention is critical in developing the fundamental building blocks of democratic participation. However, Budde et al. (2021) provide a more critical perspective, arguing that traditional pedagogical approaches, such as behavioral contracts, may inadvertently reinforce existing institutional orders rather than truly empower students.

5.3 Institutional and Systemic Challenges

Civic education's systematic challenges are multifaceted and deeply rooted in broader societal structures. Gastil and Davies' (2020) proposal for a public corporation dedicated to digital civic technology represents an innovative approach to addressing institutional limitations. Their research suggests that sustainable funding and institutional support are crucial for developing adequate civic engagement infrastructure. Kryshtanovych et al. (2021) further contextualize this challenge within the broader framework of state development, positioning civic education as a critical social and institutional formation process. Their research emphasizes the role of education in navigating the complex dynamics of globalization, technological advancement, and societal transformation.

5.4 Contemporary Challenges and Future Directions

Nassa's (2024) recent research provides critical insights into the contemporary challenges of civic education, particularly in the context of political literacy and youth engagement. The study highlights the effectiveness of interactive and contextual programs, such as political simulations and discussions, in enhancing political awareness. However, it

identifies significant barriers, including resource limitations and curriculum relevance. Habicher et al. (2021) offer an additional perspective by exploring design thinking as a transformative tool. While their research primarily focuses on organizational contexts, it suggests innovative approaches to developing democratic leadership and adaptive thinking skills that could be applied to civic education.

5.5 Integrated Approach to Democratic Character Building

The synthesized research points to the necessity of an integrated, holistic approach to civic education. This approach must simultaneously address technological, pedagogical, and systemic challenges. It requires a dynamic curriculum that:

1. Incorporates digital literacy and critical technological awareness
2. Develops comprehensive civic competencies
3. Provides interactive and contextual learning experiences
4. Addresses systemic inequalities and marginalization
5. Fosters adaptive and critical thinking skills

6. DISCUSSION

The role of civic education in democratic character building is increasingly complex and critical. Civic education must continually evolve as societies navigate rapid technological, social, and political transformations. It must serve as a mechanism for knowledge transfer and as a dynamic platform for developing critically aware, technologically literate, and actively engaged citizens. The research synthesized here demonstrates that effective civic education transcends traditional boundaries. It requires a multidimensional approach integrating technological understanding, pedagogical innovation, and a deep commitment to democratic principles. Future research and educational practices must continue to explore these intersections, developing adaptive and inclusive strategies for nurturing democratic character in an increasingly complex global landscape.

Based on the comprehensive analysis, several key recommendations emerge:

1. Develop more inclusive and adaptive digital citizenship frameworks
2. Create innovative pedagogical methods that emphasize interactive learning
3. Address technological and social barriers to civic participation
4. Enhance curriculum relevance and educational resources
5. Promote interdisciplinary approaches to civic education

7. SUGGESTIONS

This research concludes that civic education is critical in building democratic character amid complex technological, social, and political challenges. Digital transformation has changed the paradigm of civic participation, presenting both opportunities and challenges in implementing civic education. This education must integrate digital literacy, critical awareness, and participatory skills to produce responsive, educated, and democratically oriented citizens. In addition, inclusive and context-based pedagogical approaches need to be developed to respond to the needs of a dynamic young generation.

As a suggestion, future civic education needs to:

1. Develop an adaptive curriculum that emphasizes digital literacy and technological awareness.
2. Enhance interactive learning methods relevant to contemporary social and political conditions.
3. Address technological and social barriers to increase inclusive citizen participation.
4. Increase educational resources and curriculum relevance to reach more communities.
5. Promote interdisciplinary collaboration in civic education research and practice.

REFERENCES

- Armano, E., Briziarelli, M., Risi, E., Flores, J., Uluorta, H., Quill, L., Rossiter, N., Zehle, S., Cuppini, N., Frapporti, M., Pirone, M., Heiland, H., Leonardi, D., Murgia, A., Cingolani, P., Miconi, A., Cossu, A., Franke, M., Pulignano, V., & Lucciarini, S. (2022). *Digital Platforms and Algorithmic Subjectivities*.
- Budde, J., Hellberg, L., & Weuster, N. (2021). Contractualism as an element of democratic pedagogy? *Journal of Social Science Education*, 20(4), 48–71. <https://doi.org/10.11576/jsse-4468>
- Chaka, C. (2022). Digital marginalization, data marginalization, and algorithmic exclusions: a critical southern decolonial approach to datafication, algorithms, and digital citizenship from the Souths. *Journal of E-Learning and Knowledge Society*, 18(3), 83–95. <https://doi.org/10.20368/1971-8829/1135678>
- Demir, M. (2021). Alternative Assessment Methods in Primary Education: Review and Future Directions. *Current Studies in Educational Disciplines* [Internet], 227-88. In *Current Studies in Educational Disciplines*. www.isres.org
- Feriyansyah, & Maharani, S. D. (2023). Pragmatisme Pendidikan Kewargaan Digital. *Jurnal Civic Hukum*, 8(1), 28–36.

- Feser, M. S., Haak, I., & Rabe, T. (2023). *VeSP-Be – Vergleich von Studieneingangsphasen in Physik hinsichtlich des Sense of Belonging von Studierenden. Dokumentation der Erhebungsinstrumente und deren deskriptive, quantitative Ergebnisse*. 8. <https://doi.org/10.25656/01>
- Gastil, J., & Davies, T. (2020). Digital Democracy : Episode IV—A New Hope*: How a Corporation for Public Software Could Transform Digital Engagement for Government and Civil Society. *Digital Government: Research and Practice*, 1(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3342194>
- Habicher, D., Erschbamer, G., Pechlaner, H., Ghirardello, L., & Walder, M. (2021). Transformation and Design Thinking: perspectives on sustainable change, company resilience and democratic leadership in SMEs. *Leadership, Education, Personality: An Interdisciplinary Journal*, 3(2), 145–156. <https://doi.org/10.1365/s42681-022-00028-x>
- Kryshtanovych, M., Romanova, A., Koval, I., Lesko, N., & Lukashevskaya, U. (2021). Research of problems and prospects of state development in the pedagogical process. *Revista Tempos e Espaços Em Educação*, 14(33), e16534. <https://doi.org/10.20952/revtee.v14i33.16534>
- Levitsky, S., & Ziblatt, D. (2018). *How Democracies Die*. Crown. <https://books.google.co.id/books?id=TwFDwAAQBAJ>
- Magdalena, I., Haq, A. S., & Ramdhan, F. (2020). Pembelajaran Pendidikan Kewarganegaraan Di Sekolah Dasar Negeri Bojong 3 Pinang. *Jurnal Pendidikan Dan Sains*, 2(3), 418–430. <https://ejournal.stitpn.ac.id/index.php/bintang>
- Nassa, D. Y. (2024). *Mewujudkan Generasi Melek Politik Melalui Pendidikan Kewarganegaraan Dalam Menyongsong Indonesia Emas 2045*. 130–142.
- Nelsen, M. D. (2023). Lessons in Empowerment: The Civic Potential of Historically Grounded Conversations among Racially Marginalized Youth. *Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 705(1), 174–191. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00027162231188576>
- Reite, I., Biseth, H., & Huang, L. (2021). *Developing Digital Citizenship and Civic Engagement Through Social Media Use in Nordic Schools* (pp. 65–92). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-66788-7_4
- Rodríguez-Hoyos, C., Calvo-Salvador, A., Gutiérrez, A., & Blanco, G. (2023). *Youth Civic Engagement: New Strategies for Social Innovation* (pp. 328–351). <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-6684-6123-5.ch017>
- Suherlan, S. (2023). Digital Technology Transformation in Enhancing Public Participation in Democratic Processes. *Technology and Society Perspectives (TACIT)*, 1(1), 10–17. <https://doi.org/10.61100/tacit.v1i1.34>
- Widiatmaka, P. (2022). Perkembangan pendidikan kewarganegaraan (PPKn) di dalam membangun karakter bangsa peserta didik. *Civic Edu: Jurnal Pendidikan Kewarganegaraan*, 5(1), 1–10. <https://journal.unpas.ac.id/index.php/civicedu/article/download/5979/2466>
- Yawisah, U., Umam, A. K., Asas, M., & Wahyundin. (2019). Journal of Social Studies Education Research Sosial Bilgiler Eğitimi Araştırmaları Dergisi. *Journal of Social Studies Education Research*, 10(3), 364–386.

<https://jsser.org/index.php/jsser/article/view/3043>